

External Debt And Poverty Incidence In Nigeria: Error Correction Mechanism

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Abstract

This study examines external debt stock impact on poverty incidence in Nigeria. The study's data spanning from 1981 to 2018 were collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and World Bank: World Development Indicators. The variables for the study are external debt stock, debt service payments, poverty, foreign reserve, exchange rate, investment, and economic growth. The data was analysed using the Error Correction Mechanism. ADF and PP were applied to test for the stationarity while the long-run relationship was examined through the ARDL Bound Test. The results showed that the variables are integrated of order one. External debt stock has a significant positive impact on poverty, debt service payments and poverty incidence in Nigeria. The study therefore submitted that large stock of foreign debt and debt service payments are not desirable for the growth of Nigeria's economy. Therefore, the study acclaims that government needs to reduce the accumulation of debts and its burden. Debt Management Office should reduce the national poverty threshold from the minimum level of 25% of GDP to something lower. This will caution the government from securing loans which throws the nation into debt servitude and impoverishes its citizens.

Keywords: External Debt, Poverty Incidence, Error Correction Mechanism, Debt Service.

1. INTRODUCTION

The challenge of foreign debt of developing economies is a serious concern of which Nigeria as a nation is not exempted from this problem. Nigeria is among the developing economies and as a lower middle-income country was and is still faced with the problem of adequate domestic savings which could cater for her economic development programme. With the low level of national savings of the economy, investment is automatically low and this lead to low production and unavoidably result in a situation whereby the country is in an annual poverty circulation.

The problem of external debt in LDCs stems from the debt crisis that occurred in 1970 – 1983 which was majorly caused by the oil-price shocks, bad macroeconomic management of LDCs, policies of developed countries and their banks against LDCs, rising interest rates, and trade policies which left LDCs balance of payment (BOP) unbalance and in pursuance of balancing their BOP, huge external debts that they found difficult to repay in the form of interest and principal were accumulated. This scenario worsens the poverty level of LDCs which include Nigeria, as foreign exchange reserves of many LDCs were depleted. Consequently, most developed countries are left with no choice but to waive a major part of the debt for the LDCs and this was when most LDCs experienced debt forgiveness which Nigeria experienced during the regime of former President Olusegun Obasanjo.

However, Nigeria's economy is largely considered as a rural and agricultural-based traditional sector that comprises a greater proportion of its population living in penury. The country is only featured with a small urban and capital-intensive sector that has been a beneficiary of the country's resources in form of exploitation of mineral resources such as crude oil, production of services rendered by successive governments which includes road amenities, and few social infrastructures.

As the case has been in a good number of African countries, the traditional sector of the economy has always been the private agricultural sector which was and is still being done on a small scale as it is characterized by poor and informal farmers. However, the formal, capital-intensive sector has a few transnational firms coupled with a myriad of small local industries and government agencies/corporations working in virtually all areas of the economy. This has increased the income inequality gap between the traditional and urban sector of the economy as formal, urban, and capital intensive sector jobs are lucrative and secure but very scarce while the traditional are left with no infrastructures to enhance growth hence leads to a severe poverty incidence in the traditional sector. Moreover, the popular saying goes that the presence of poverty in any area or aspect of the economy is poverty in the whole economy as the impoverished sector could bring down the rich aspect of the economy.

For many years now, researchers have attempted to unravel the issues behind external debt and economic growth in Nigeria, public debt and poverty incidence, economic growth, and poverty incidence in Nigeria. However, looking at external debt issue from the perspective of the Two-Gap Model, one could find out that there is a need for Nigeria whose savings could not cater for its investment (savings gap) and its shortage of foreign earnings against its foreign exchange requirements (foreign exchange gap) must secure foreign aids to close these gaps. All things being equal, this could lead to the case of rising foreign debt in the Nigerian economy. Debt, therefore, is seen as the dissimilarity amidst the sum of all government borrowings from the private sector/individuals of the country or by foreigners/international bodies, whether interest-bearing or not, and all government loans to private individuals at home or abroad (Oyejide, Soyede, and Kayode, 1985). However, World Bank (2004) categorized the sources of debt into two which are internal and external. An internal source of debt is associated with internal debt which is the totality of all residential loans to the government while an external source relates with external debt and it is the sum of all non-residential loans to the government which is payable in terms of foreign currency.

According to Debt Management Office (DMO, 2018), the external debt profile of Nigeria rose to \$24.274 billion (approximately ₦7.7 trillion) in the year 2018 against the \$19 billion in the year 2017. However, the huge increase in the debt stock of Nigeria did not translate into viable economic growth as the country was still categorized as a developing economy with a high level of poverty in the country. Moreover, the sum of all foreign debt principal repayment at the closure of the year 2018 was \$712.75 million compared to \$124.29 million in the last month of the year 2017 which is a reflection of \$588.45 million or a 473.44% increase. This huge repayment eats deep into the national income of the country. Also, the aggregate external debt interest payment at the end of the year 2018, amounted to \$687.80 million, against \$279.74 million at the end of the year 2017. This shows that there is an increase of \$408.07 million or 145.87% rise in foreign debt interest payment, which was mainly due to interest payment made on Eurobonds.

There have been various arguments on external debt influence on the economy and most point at the positive impact of foreign debt on economic growth as capital flows in through it and when channeled towards productive activities, economic growth is enhanced while others were of the view that through credit-rationing issue and debt overhang, accumulation of external debt may hurt investment (Eduardo, 1989).

Udoka and Ogege (2012) study the extent of the external debt crisis and its consequential effect on economic development using Nigerian economy data from 1970 to 2010. Error correction mechanism with co-integration estimation is used to test the relationship between per-capita GDP and other macroeconomic variables (foreign reserve, debt stock, investment, debt service payment) was adopted. The result showed that political instability is

detrimental to development and other variables such as debt stock, and debt servicing were responsible for the underperforming of the economy. Hence, the study recommended that external debt should be reduced to a minimal level to avoid economic degradation. This study however did not delve into poverty and external debt issue in Nigeria.

Obademi (2013) uses time-series data of Nigeria between 1970 - 2009 to examine external debt-growth nexus. The study showed that no long-run relationship existed between foreign debt and economic growth in Nigeria. However, the study indicates that external debt could lead to a decrease in GDP, thus, it was recommended that government should enact strong policies that will improve better management of external debts.

Nwanne and Eze (2015) examine the correlation among external debt servicing, external debt receipt and exchange rate volatility in Nigeria for the period of 1981 through 2013. The study revealed that external debt receipts and external debt servicing are positively correlated with exchange rate volatility in both short-run and long-run. The study, therefore, concluded that foreign debt receipts and foreign debt services influence exchange rate positively.

Matthew and Mordecai (2016) examine the effect of public debt on the economic development of Nigeria with annual time series data from 1986 to 2014. Augmented Dickey-Fuller test for stationarity, Johansen co-integration test for long-run association, Error Correction Model (ECM) for both short-run and long-run analytical impact, and the Granger Causality test for causal effect analysis were employed in the study. The co-integration test results revealed the existence of a long-run relationship among the variables of the study namely; external debt stock, domestic debt stock, external debt servicing, domestic debt servicing, and economic development (measured as per capita GDP) in the Nigeria economy. The short-run analysis results indicated that Nigeria economic development is insignificantly negatively related to external debt stock and external debt servicing, more so, Nigeria economic development is directly and significantly related with domestic debt stock however, Nigeria economic development is significantly inversely related with domestic debt service payment. The study thus concluded that reduction of external debt accumulation and domestic debt accumulation will improve economic development.

Studies carried out by Ndubuisi (2017), Suleiman and Azeez (2012) on external debt and Nigeria economic growth found that economic growth is positively and significantly impacted by external debt but Udeh, Ugwu, and Onwuka (2016) found a positive nexus between externally sourced debt and economic growth in the short-run but a negative relationship in the long-run while Maryam (2017) and Utomi (2014) found external debt to be insignificantly impacting the Nigeria economic growth positively and insignificant long-run association between external debt and economic growth respectively. Also, studies carried out by Festus and Saibu (2019) find that external debt hurts Nigeria economic growth. Various researches have been conducted on the effect of external debt on Nigeria economic growth but very few of them have looked into external debt and poverty incidence in Nigeria. In this regard, Akpan and Elijah (2015) find that public debt debars growth and increases poverty, Oyegoke and Wasiu (2018) found that economic growth impact negatively on poverty incidence in Nigeria. Also, Tamunonimim (2014) find a long-run significant relationship between poverty and internal debt in Nigeria while John Bosco (2018) find that public debt induces a significant positive impact on poverty headcount in Nigeria.

Udofia and Akpanah (2016) investigate the external debt impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study adopts an error correction mechanism on Nigeria data for 1980 through 2012. The study affirmed the traditional view of debt's impact on economic growth. Furthermore, the study showed that debt overhang problem does not exist in the Nigerian context. It was therefore recommended from the findings that Nigerian developmental activities should be funded through increased export earnings spearheaded by export-led growth strategy and investment in human capital as these could be a substitute for future external loans.

Following the related studies, the external debt-growth relationship remains controversial while the effect of external debt on poverty index remains scanty in literature. The

current rise in external debt profile and poverty index in Nigeria calls for investigation. This paper, therefore, tries to fill this knowledge gap.

2. METHODS

There are various theories and school of thoughts in economics advocating poverty reduction in so many ways: The Classical Welfare Economists (Adam Smith, Karl Max, etc.) opined that people's welfare and wealth is determined by the output per labour as well as their purchasing power over other people's labour. In other words, an increase in workers' welfare is dependent on higher labour which leads to higher output and income. This research is therefore premised on the Keynesian ideology which justified that poverty is an involuntary and undesirable outcome of unemployment. It is on this note that the study adopts the two-gap model by Chenery (1956).

The two gaps are explained in terms of a national income accounting identity. This is mathematically expressed as:

$$Y_t = C_t + I_t + X_t - M_t \quad (i)$$

$$Y_t = C_t + S_t \quad (ii)$$

$$S_t = Y_t - C_t \quad (iii)$$

Collecting the likes term of injection and leakages in the economy, the equation changed to

$$C_t + I_t + X_t = M_t - C_t + S_t \quad (iv)$$

$$I_t - S_t = M_t - X_t \quad (v)$$

Where:

Y_t = current national income or expenditure

C_t = current consumption expenditure

I_t = current investment expenditure

X_t = current export

M_t = current import

S_t = current savings

$I_t - S_t$ represents the savings gap in the economy while $M_t - X_t$ denotes the foreign exchange gap in the economy. It is succinct to note according to Chenery that when $I_t - S_t > M_t - X_t$, the economy is facing the problem of savings constraints but when $I_t - S_t < M_t - X_t$ the economy is faced with the challenge of foreign exchange constraints. Whichever way this goes; foreign aid could be used to bridge these gaps as it will increase capital inflow into the economy.

Data Sources and Method of Analysis

This study employed secondary data. It sourced annual time series data from the Central Bank of Nigeria Annual Statistical Bulletin 2018 and World Bank (World Development Indicators (WDI)) from 1981 – 2018. The study used Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test to test for the stationarity of the data, ARDL Bound test for co-integration was used to determine the long-run relationship among the variables using the Error Correction Mechanism.

Model Specification

The functional relationship between the explained and the independent variables is expressed as:

$$POV = f(EXDS, DSP, EXR, FOREX, EG, INV) \quad (1)$$

Mathematically, the relationship could be expressed as:

$$POV_t = \alpha + \gamma EXDS_t + \theta DSP_t + \rho EXR_t + \tau FOREX_t + \phi EG_t + \omega INV_t \quad (2)$$

The relationship could be expressed econometrically as:

$$POV_t = \alpha + \gamma EXDS_t + \theta DSP_t + \rho EXR_t + \tau FOREX_t + \phi EG_t + \omega INV_t + \mu_t \quad (3)$$

All variables were logged to ensure that they are all on the same unit of measurement.

$$\ln POV_t = \alpha + \gamma \ln EXDS_t + \theta \ln DSP_t + \rho EXR_t + \tau \ln FOREX_t + \phi EG_t + \omega \ln INV_t + \mu_t \quad (4)$$

Where:

Poverty = POV

External Debt Stock	=	EXDS
Debt Service Payment	=	DSP
Exchange Rate	=	EXR
Foreign Reserves	=	FOREX
Economic Growth	=	EG
Investment	=	INV
Disturbance term	=	μ
The intercept	=	α
The slopes of short-run parameters	=	$\gamma, \theta, \rho, \tau, \varphi, \omega$

A priori expectations

$$\alpha > 0, \gamma > 0, \theta > 0, \rho > 0, \tau < 0, \varphi < 0, \omega < 0$$

Data Description

Table 1: Variable description and sources

Variable/Notation	Description	Source
Poverty (POV)	Poverty is measured in terms of real per capita gross domestic product	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)
External Debt Stock (EXDS)	Total annual external debt stocks	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)
Debt Service Payment (DSP)	Total annual external debt service payment	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)
Exchange Rate (EXR)	This is measured in Naira per Dollar terms	Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) 2018
Foreign Reserves (FOREX)	This is the annual foreign earnings	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)
Economic Growth (EG)	This is the annual change in RGDP	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)
Investment (INV)	This is the annual gross fixed capital formation in the economy.	World Bank: World Development Indicators (2019)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Stationarity Test

Time series data are faced with the stationarity problem and as it is widely known that most economic data are differenced stationary. Therefore, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and the Phillips-Perron (PP) tests are used to test for stationarity. The choice of these two methods was chosen as both methods state null hypothesis that a time series is difference stationary $\{i. e. y_t \text{ is } I(0)\}$.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	ADF Test			Descriptive Stat.			
	Level	1 st diff	Remarks	μ	σ	JB	Obs
LNPOV	-2.732(0.078)	-5.361(0.000)**	I(1)	3.87	1.87	7.21	38
LNEXDS	-2.045(0.267)	-4.071(0.003)**	I(1)	23.43	0.73	4.38	38
LN DSP	-3.807(0.006)*		I(0)	21.39	0.65	0.06	38
EXR	0.984(0.995)	-5.369(0.000)**	I(1)	97.06	87.67	4.04	38
LNFOREX	-1.395(0.573)	-5.058(0.000)**	I(1)	9.06	1.34	1.73	38
EG	-3.081(0.037)*		I(0)	0.54	5.39	8.96	38
LNINV	-2.204(0.208)	-4.110(0.003)**	I(1)	24.73	0.21	3.85	38
Variable	PP Test			Descriptive Stat.			
	Level	1 st diff	Remarks	μ	σ	JB	Obs
LNPOV	-2.855(0.060)	-5.482(0.000)**	I(1)	3.87	1.87	7.21	38
LNEXDS	-1.920(0.319)	-4.007(0.003)**	I(1)	23.43	0.73	4.38	38
LN DSP	-3.757(0.007)*		I(0)	21.39	0.65	0.06	38
EXR	1.344(0.998)	-5.357(0.000)**	I(1)	97.06	87.67	4.04	38
LNFOREX	-0.881(0.782)	-6.651(0.000)**	I(1)	9.06	1.34	1.73	38
EG	-4.150(0.002)*		I(0)	0.54	5.39	8.96	38
LNINV	-3.505(0.013)*		I(0)	24.73	0.21	3.85	38

Source: Author's computation

* and ** indicates stationarity at levels and 1st difference respectively using 95% level of significance. Where μ = mean and σ = standard deviation. Figures in parenthesis are the MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

The table above shows the results of ADF and PP unit root tests. The two methods of unit root tests conformed to their result except for LNINV that was stationary at the first difference using the ADF test but stationary at levels using the PP test. In other words, the variables are found to be integrated into the order I(0) and I(1). Hence, they were subjected to a co-integration test to determine if they are cointegrated. Consequently, ARDL bound test approach for co-integration was applied.

The table also shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. Mean is the average value of the series by dividing the sum of the values of the series by the number of observations. The results showed that LNPOV (Poverty: Per capita RGDP), LNEXTS (External Debt Stock), LNDSP (Debt Service Payments), EXR (Exchange rate), LNFOREX (Foreign reserve), EG (Economic growth), and LNINV (Investment) are 3.87, 23.43, 21.39, 97.06, 9.06, 0.54 and 24.73 respectively. The standard deviation for LNPOV (Poverty: Per capita RGDP), LNEXTS (External Debt Stock), LNDSP (Debt Service Payments), EXR (Exchange rate), LNFOREX (Foreign reserve), EG (Economic growth), and LNINV (Investment) are 1.87, 0.73, 0.65, 87.67, 1.34, 5.39 and 0.21 respectively.

Also, the Jarque-Bera test statistic was used to test for the normality of the distribution of the series. It measures the difference between the skewness and kurtosis of the series with those with normal distribution. The Jarque-Bera for LNPOV (Poverty: Per capita RGDP), LNEXTS (External Debt Stock), LNDSP (Debt Service Payments), EXR (Exchange rate), LNFOREX (Foreign reserve), EG (Economic growth), and LNINV (Investment) are 7.21, 4.38, 0.06, 4.04, 1.73, 8.96 and 3.85 respectively.

Lag Selection Criteria

Conversely, there is a need to determine the optimal lag before estimating the model. The optimal lag is presented in the table below and is the result of various lag selection criteria estimated through the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model.

Table 3: VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Dependent variable(s): LNPOV

Independent variables: C LNEXTS LNDSP EXR LNFOREX EG LNINV

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-35.48092	NA	0.667023	2.427481	2.738551	2.534862
1	1.484114	57.03177*	0.085664*	0.372336	0.727844*	0.495058*
2	2.155477	0.997453	0.087602	0.391116	0.791062	0.529177
3	3.488417	1.904201	0.086343	0.372090*	0.816476	0.525492

Source: Author's computation

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

From the table above, the result reveals that four out of the five selection criteria LR, FPE, SC, and HQ show that the optimal lag is 1 while only AIC gives 3 as the optimal lag length for the model. The study hereby chose 3 as the optimal lag length as AIC gives for consistency with former usage of AIC in previous analysis conducted.

Co-integration Test

The co-integration test is used to test for the long-run associations between the dependent and the independent variables. The study employed the use of the ARDL bound test for co-integration since the stationarity is a combination of I(0) and I(1).

Table 4: F-Bounds Test Result

Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship

Test Statistic	Value	Significance	I(0)	I(1)
Asymptotic: n=1000				
F-statistic	5.061960	10%	2.12	3.23
K	6	5%	2.45	3.61
		1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Author's computation

Where: k is the degree of freedom.

The result above showed that there is a long-run relationship among the variables as the value of F-statistic of 5.061 is greater than the I(1) critical value bound at 1% which is 4.43. As the condition of the ARDL bound test for the rejecting of the null hypothesis is met, it is, therefore, succinct to conclude that there is a strong long-term movement amidst the variables.

Long-run Analysis**Table 5: Ordinary Least Squares Result**

Dependent Variable: LNPOV

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.612600	30.88150	0.019837	0.9845
LNPOV(-1)	0.070391	0.342721	0.205388	0.8404
LNPOV(-2)	0.851872	0.501339	1.699193	0.1131
LNPOV(-3)	0.308348	0.340845	0.904656	0.3821
LNEXDS(-1)	-0.919865	0.309513	-2.971980	0.0108
LNEXDS(-2)	0.989179	0.486173	2.034621	0.0628
LNEXDS(-3)	0.336499	0.414340	0.812134	0.4313
LNDS(-1)	-0.335719	0.160919	-2.086254	0.0572
LNDS(-2)	-0.415029	0.191119	-2.171574	0.0490
LNDS(-3)	0.095995	0.156599	0.613002	0.5504
EXR(-1)	-0.006373	0.003865	-1.648711	0.1231
EXR(-2)	0.008630	0.006337	1.361931	0.1964
EXR(-3)	0.008084	0.008073	1.001379	0.3349
LNFOREX(-1)	-0.091406	0.224479	-0.407189	0.6905
LNFOREX(-2)	-0.265432	0.208618	-1.272334	0.2255
LNFOREX(-3)	0.363358	0.173770	2.091026	0.0567
EG(-1)	0.029767	0.024372	1.221374	0.2436
EG(-2)	0.009669	0.021758	0.444384	0.6641
EG(-3)	-0.026919	0.020001	-1.345894	0.2013
LNINV(-1)	-0.590476	0.656623	-0.899262	0.3849
LNINV(-2)	0.958356	0.795100	1.205328	0.2496
LNINV(-3)	-0.295331	0.745665	-0.396064	0.6985
R-squared	0.988877	Mean dependent var		3.540907
Adjusted R-squared	0.970910	S.D. dependent var		1.530771
S.E. of regression	0.261085	Akaike info criterion		0.418806
Sum squared resid	0.886153	Schwarz criterion		1.396453
Log likelihood	14.67090	Hannan-Quinn criter.		0.756289
F-statistic	55.03730	Durbin-Watson stat		1.893421
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
LM Test	0.051(0.9839)			
Heteroskedasticity Test	1.133(0.418)			

Source: Author's computation

Table 5 presents the results of the long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables. Since the real per capita GDP is used to capture poverty, results obtained will be interpreted indirectly or inversely. It reveals that the level of poverty in the previous period does not have a significant impact on the current level of poverty in the country but has a positive impact on the poverty level which implies that the lag value of poverty influences the poverty level in the current period in the long-run.

The result showed that the lag value of external debt stock has a significant positive impact on the poverty level in the country as an increase in external debt stock leads to a reduction in real per capita GDP and thus leads to an increase in poverty in the long run. This finding agrees with the finding of Obademi (2013) who found that increase in external debt could result in to decrease in GDP and the finding of Hassan, Sule, and Abu (2015) who found that if the debt accumulation is not checked, the economy will further fall into a worse state: leading to surplus budgeting, and overheating; unemployment increase, crowding-out of investment, falling external reserves, exchange rate depreciation, higher inflation and finally the high rate of poverty incidence in the economy. The finding also conforms with the finding of Akpan and Elijah (2015) who found that external debt had a negative impact on growth and poverty reduction.

However, poverty level is significantly positively impacted by debt service payment. Debt servicing reduces the per capita income and thus increases the poverty level in the country in the long run. This finding conforms with the findings of Adesola (2009) who established that external debt servicing has a significant negative influence on gross domestic product and gross fixed capital formation in Nigeria and this increases the level of poverty in the country. Moreover, exchange rate, foreign reserve, economic growth, and investment do not have a significant impact on the poverty level in the long run.

The R-squared of 0.9888 and adjusted R-squared of 0.9709 shows that there is good goodness of fit of the regression line. The R-squared showed that 98.8% of the variation that occurs in poverty is explained by the explanatory variables. Also, using the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test, the result showed that the residuals of the model is not suffering from the autocorrelation problem as the p-value 0.9839 of the result is greater than the 0.05% significance level. This, therefore, implies that the long-run model is not suffering from autocorrelation. A post-test of heteroscedasticity was also conducted and the result revealed that there is an absence of heteroscedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroscedasticity Test in which its p-value is 0.418, hence, the null hypothesis that the squared residuals of the model are not heteroskedastic (unequal variance) is therefore rejected and accept the alternative that the squared residuals are homoscedastic.

Stability Test of the Long-run Parameters

Figure 1: Long-run model CUSUM and CUSUMSQ graphs for stability

The study also checked for the stability of the model using the CUSUM and CUSUM of squares test at 5% significance level. The result showed that the long-run model is stable over time as the CUSUM and CUSUMSQ indicated the absence of structural break in the model at 5% level of significance.

Parsimonious Error Correction Model (Short-run Parameters Analysis)

Table 6: Ordinary Least Squares Result

Dependent Variable: D(LNPOV)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.004508	0.063480	-0.071011	0.9442
D(LNPOV(-2))	1.059999	0.247856	4.276664	0.0005
D(LNEXDS(-1))	-0.935933	0.219606	-4.261879	0.0005
D(LNEXDS(-2))	0.820270	0.248203	3.304831	0.0039
D(LNEXDS(-3))	0.491689	0.201336	2.442130	0.0251
D(LNDSP(-1))	-0.344850	0.113761	-3.031368	0.0072
D(LNDSP(-2))	-0.471439	0.126229	-3.734798	0.0015
D(EXR(-1))	-0.005689	0.002534	-2.244815	0.0376
D(EXR(-2))	0.010765	0.003015	3.569928	0.0022
D(LNFOREX(-2))	-0.366976	0.108861	-3.371058	0.0034
D(LNFOREX(-3))	0.359334	0.106545	3.372589	0.0034
D(EG(-1))	0.027488	0.012114	2.269089	0.0358
D(EG(-3))	-0.022410	0.011000	-2.037261	0.0566
D(LNINV(-1))	-0.495797	0.410928	-1.206531	0.2432
D(LNINV(-2))	0.796789	0.399776	1.993088	0.0616
ECM(-1)	-0.948171	0.294038	-3.224649	0.0047
R-squared	0.674436	Mean dependent var	-	

Adjusted R-squared	0.403132	S.D. dependent var	0.158877
S.E. of regression	0.243128	Akaike info criterion	0.314699
Sum squared resid	1.063999	Schwarz criterion	1.033014
Log likelihood	10.64964	Hannan-Quinn criter.	0.559684
F-statistic	2.485908	Durbin-Watson stat	2.062898
Prob(F-statistic)	0.034107		
LM Test	0.1636(0.9192)		
Heteroskedasticity Test	0.8923(0.5837)		

Source: Author's computation

The table above shows the outcome of the parsimonious error correction model to further analyse the long-run relationship between the dependent and the independent variables and to determine the short-run relationships of the parameters from the long-run equilibrium by incorporating the residuals lagged which is the error correction term. Since the real per capita gross domestic product is used to capture poverty, results obtained will be interpreted indirectly. It revealed that the level of poverty in the lag period does have a significant positive impact on the current level of poverty in the country in the short run. The result implies that the previous poverty level has a significant positive impact on the current poverty level.

The results showed that the external debt stock has a significant positive impact on the poverty level in the first lag but a significant negative impact with poverty in the second and third lag periods. Moreso, debt service payment has a significant positive impact on the poverty level. Debt servicing reduces the per capita income and thus increases the poverty level in the country in the short run.

Moreover, the exchange rate has a significant positive impact on poverty as an increase in exchange or appreciation of domestic currency leads to a reduction in export, and an increase in imports leads to a reduction in income. Also, the foreign reserve has a significant positive impact on poverty in the second lag but a negative impact in its third lag.

Economic growth, however, has a significant negative impact on the poverty level in Nigeria as an increase in the growth rate leads to the provision of more social amenities and an increase in income in the economy. Investment does not have a significant impact on the poverty level which aligns with the long-run result.

The error correction coefficient is correctly signed and significant with the value of -0.9481. This reveals that the speed of adjustment back to equilibrium as a result of any short-run shock is approximately 94.81 percent annually.

The R-squared of 0.6744 shows the fitness of the regression in the model to be fairly good. The R-squared showed that 67.44% of the variation that occurs in poverty is explained by the explanatory variables. Also, using the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test, the result showed that the residuals of the model is not suffering from serial correlation as the p-value 0.9192 of the result is greater than the 0.05% significance level. This, therefore, implies that the error correction model is not suffering from autocorrelation. A post-test of heteroskedasticity was also conducted and the result revealed that there is absence of heteroskedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity Test in which its p-value is 0.5837, hence the null hypothesis that the squared residuals of the model are heteroskedastic is therefore rejected and accept the alternative that the squared residuals are homoskedastic.

Stability Test of the Long-run Parameters

Figure 2: Short-run model CUSUM and CUSUMS of Squares graphs for stability

The study also checked for the stability of the model using the CUSUM and CUSUM of squares test at 5% significance level. The result showed that the model is stable over time as the CUSUM indicated the absence of structural break in the model at 5% level of significance but the CUSUMS of Squares indicated the presence of a structural break in the model at 5% level of significance but this does not render the validity of the results invalid. However, this deviation could be a result of a sharp fall in the external debt series which occurred in the year 2005 where the external debt of Nigeria falls significantly.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is succinct to conclude that external debt stock, as well as debt servicing, has a negative impact on the economy as it increases the poverty level in the country. Most developing nations including Nigeria are burdened with external debt problems to bridge the gap or difference in their internal and external disequilibrium. This turns out to be worrisome as it increases their debt profiles and worsens the economy as they ended up with service debts through payment of huge interest and principal. This study, therefore, examined the impact of external debt stock on poverty incidence in Nigeria. The study affirms that external debt stock and debt servicing have a positive impact on poverty in the Nigerian economy i.e. as external debt stock and debt service payment continues to increase, more poverty incidence is recorded in the country.

Following the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Government should ensure that external debt is reduced significantly as it influences positively the incidence of poverty in the country.
- ii. The Debt Management Office should reduce the national poverty threshold of the nation to at least the minimum level of 25% of GDP as it serves as an effective way of cautioning the government from securing external loans which throws the nation into debt servitude in the long run and impoverished her citizens.

- iii. External loans contracted should be used on productive economic activities that could pay back the principal and the interest of such loans to stimulate the growth in the country.
- iv. The acquisition of external loans should aim towards the growth and development of the economy and not for any political reason in the country.

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